

Next-Generation Sequencing at The Frontline of The COVID-19 Battle

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Next-generation sequencing (NGS) refers to sequencing technologies developed a few decades after the first-generation sequencing, known mainly as Sanger method, developed by the British biochemist Fred Sanger and his colleagues in 1977, and based on the selective incorporation of chain-terminating nucleotides, dideoxynucleotides (ddNTPs), by DNA polymerase during in vitro DNA replication. The random termination events during the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) result in the accumulation of fragments of varying lengths (differ ideally only by one nucleotide), which are separated by size via gel electrophoresis. The order of the nucleotides in the separated DNA fragments is subsequently determined by analysing the gel. Radioactive labelled ddNTPs, later on substituted by fluorescently marked ddNTPs (dye-labelled terminators), enable to reveal which nucleotide is present at each band location. DNA synthesis and signal detection that determines the type of the incorporated nucleotide into the amplified chain, are separately performed in the Sanger method.

The Sanger method can process sequencing only of a single DNA fragment (typically sequence reads of 500-900 base pairs) at a time, and thus, for example in the hierarchical shotgun method (also called clone-by-clone method), thousands of DNA fragments of a genome (typically ~ 200,000 base pairs of length) need to be cloned separately in bacterial artificial chromosomes (BACs). Shorter fragments from each BAC are then subcloned into plasmids, and each plasmid is then individually sequenced. The sequenced overlapping fragments are assembled to build the BAC sequence they originated from, and overlapping BAC sequences are assembled to reconstruct the whole genome.

In contrast, NGS enables the analysis of an entire genome in a single sequencing experiment without the need of cloning; it enables sequencing of millions to billions of DNA fragments in parallel (all at the same time), starting with a very low input DNA (in nanogram range), and DNA synthesis and signal detection of the incorporated nucleotides are performed simultaneously during the sequencing process. The parallelisation of a high number of sequencing reactions by NGS was achieved by the miniaturization of sequencing reactions and tools; the development of microfluidics, improvement of optic and detection systems, and the development of nucleotide reversible terminators that temporarily terminate the polymerase reaction.

Briefly, short DNA fragments of a whole genome are ligated to adapter sequences, and each fragment is then captured at a discrete miniature position on a solid surface, such as a glass slide, coated with oligonucleotide sequences complementary to the ligated adapter. Each glass slide enables binding of millions of DNA fragments, each at a discrete miniature place. After an initial amplification of each fragment to create a cluster of hundreds of copies, sequencing by DNA synthesis of the cluster templates starts by using exclusively dNTPs containing reversible terminators of chain elongation. Different labelling of each dNTP type enables their discrimination by specific detectors. The synthesis is transiently stopped after the incorporation of each fluorescent-labelled dNTP into the synthesized chain, to enable image uptake of each colour by a highly sensitive camera. Afterwards the dye along with the terminal 3'-blocker is chemically removed from the DNA, allowing the next synthesis cycle to commence. Usually, 100 to few hundreds cycles are performed (accordingly sequence reads of 100 to few hundreds can be performed).

Sanger sequencing
(clone-by-clone sequencing)

Next-Generation sequencing

Figure legend

Comparison between Sanger sequencing (here the hierarchical shotgun or clone-by-clone sequencing method) and Next-Generation sequencing (NGS). The Sanger method can process sequencing only of a single DNA fragment at a time. NGS enables sequencing of millions of fragments (the entire fragmented genome) in a single sequencing reactions, without the need of cloning.

Hence, NGS rendered sequencing much faster and cheaper. For instance, the first sequencing of the entire human genome (lunched in 1990) using Sanger method cost more than \$3 billion and took more than 13 years to accomplish. In contrast, NGS enables nowadays whole genome sequencing in hours and for less than \$1000.

NGS revolutionized infectious disease diagnostics

Conventional infectious disease diagnostics require the isolation of the pathogen alive and its expansion; a time-consuming, cost-intensive and a potentially hazardous process. For novel unknown pathogens, additional time and effort might be required to establish at first an appropriate culture medium that enables the specific growth of the novel bacterium, or cell line that is not only susceptible to the novel virus (the virus can enter it but not replicate) but also permissive (allows replication of the virus). In addition, work with viable pathogens that can cause serious and potentially lethal diseases needs to be done in special laboratories with biosafety level 3 or 4, which further restricts and slows the work and increases the costs.

WGS by NGS enables an easy, more accurate, and very fast identification and classification of novel pathogens, in the range of hours to few days, without any prior knowledge of those pathogens nor the need to isolate and culture them. For instance, in the case of respiratory infections, a tiny amount of pathogen DNA or RNA isolated using a swab from nasopharynx or throat is sufficient to perform WGS by NGS, and subsequently identify the pathogen.

Hence, when a cluster of pneumonia cases with an unknown cause started to be recognized as serious threat from 21 December 2019 in Wuhan, the capital of Hubei province in China, it was NGS that enabled fast identification of the causing agent. As early as 2 weeks (on 3 January 2020) after the report of the first cases, the first complete genome of the pneumonia-causing pathogen was sequenced by scientists of the National Institute of Viral Disease Control and Prevention (Beijing, China) from samples of bronchoalveolar lavage fluid (BALF) from a patient, and identified, through phylogenetic analysis, as a novel β genus coronaviruses, referred to as '2019-nCoV', and later renamed as Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) and the disease caused by this virus as Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). The identified whole genome sequence of the new coronavirus, SARS-CoV-2, was made publicly available on 12 January 2020.

Afterwards, NGS has been applied worldwide to sequence genomes of SARS-CoV-2 from samples isolated from infected people around the Globus, enabling an unprecedented real time surveillance of COVID-19 clusters and the emergence of SARS-CoV-2 variants. The rapid WGS by NGS enabled live watching of the life of SARS-CoV-2, which helped to update public health and safety measures to contain the pandemic.

No other organism has been so extensively sequenced in a short time as is the case of SARS-CoV-2. From January 2020 until 23 October 2021, as much as 4,540,501 SARS-CoV-2 genome sequences have been uploaded to the Global Initiative on Sharing Avian Influenza Data (GISAID) database, not counting unpublished sequenced genomes. UK alone has reached by 11 October 2021 the deposition of one million SARS-CoV-2 genome sequences into the GISAID database, accounting for nearly a quarter of all sequences published globally.

All measures to defeat COVID-19 started with the identification of the whole genome of SARS-CoV-2

Diagnostic assays of SARS-CoV-2

One of the first vital measures to monitor, control and suppress the spread of infectious diseases, such as COVID-19, and manage treatment of patients, is the development of appropriate assays to identify infected individuals. Infections can be tracked by detecting pathogen's nucleic acids (molecular assays), antigens (immunological assays), or antibodies (serological assays). The development of those diagnostic assays requires knowledge of the genetic information of the pathogen. The more genetic information we can read, the more accurate and specific diagnostic assays and treatments can be developed.

NGS enabled fast WGS of SARS-CoV-2, which in turn allowed fast development of specific and reliable diagnostic assays. It has enabled the design and update of SARS-CoV-2-specific probes and primers for molecular-based assays, such as real-time PCR (RT-PCR), which has been globally used to identify and quarantine infected individuals.

For instance, as early as 3 weeks after the report of the first COVID-19 cases in China, the World Health Organisation (WHO) published the first protocol for an RT-PCR assay to diagnose SARS-CoV-2.

Moreover, WGS of SARS-CoV-2 enabled and accelerated the selection and recombinant production of immunological relevant proteins, such as nucleocapsid and spike proteins, that have been used to develop immunological and serological assays for the detection of SARS-CoV-2 antigens and antibodies, respectively.

Development of vaccines against COVID-19

WGS contributed significantly to a fast design and development of vaccines against COVID-19, especially subunit vaccines such as Pfizer-BioNTech, Moderna and Johnson & Johnson's Janssen, which have been authorized for emergency use. WGS of SARS-CoV-2 enabled through computational and phylogenetic sequence analyses early selection of the spike protein as appropriate target for vaccines against COVID-19, without the need to isolate and culture SARS-CoV-2. Using sequence data, genes encoding for the wildtype or modified/optimized spike proteins could be engineered and expressed recombinantly using heterologous expression system, enabling in vitro and in vivo studies to measure their immunogenicity.

Early tracking of SARS-CoV-2 variants

The continuous WGS of millions of SARS-CoV-2 genomes around the world has enabled early identification of 'mutated' strains, tracking their transmission routes, and subsequently the implementation of appropriate measures to restrain their spread. For instance, WGS enabled early detection and track of emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants, such as the Alpha variant (B.1.1.7) (first documentation in UK in September 2020), the Beta variant (B.1.351) initially documented in South Africa in May 2020, the Gamma variant (P.1) originally recognized in Brazil in November 2020, and the Delta variant (B.1.617.2) (initial documentation in India in October 2020). WGS revealed, among others, mutations in the spike protein of those variants with potential impact on transmission ability, disease severity, and immunity.

Thus, continuous surveillance of WGS of SARS-CoV-2 is necessary to predict and identify in early stages emerging escape mutants against which established vaccines won't be effective, and thus to enable in time the update of vaccine formulations to increase efficiency against those mutants.

Development of drugs against COVID-19

WGS combined with appropriate software analysis tools provide gene and proteomic data of paramount importance, which can be used for the prediction, identification, and functional and structural annotation of viral proteins, and thus enables to identify potential targets for antiviral drugs. For instance, the predicted structure of the RNA polymerase of a novel virus can help to make a prognosis about the efficiency of already existing inhibitors of RNA polymerases that can block virus replication, or to design new specific inhibitors against the novel RNA polymerase.

In addition, as was the case for the development of vaccines against COVID-19, WGS of SARS-CoV-2 enabled early selection of the spike protein as appropriate target for the development of monoclonal antibody therapies against COVID-19. Several monoclonal antibodies that bind to specific spike epitopes have been developed and authorized for emergency use, such as sotrovimab, combination of bamlanivimab and etesevimab, and REGEN-COV (combination of casirivimab and imdevimab).

Conclusion

Time- and cost-efficiency of NGS has enabled the implementation of whole genome sequencing as affordable, indispensable, and powerful routine tool in clinical medicine and public health. In the current COVID-19 battle, NGS has enabled:

- 1) The identification of SARS-CoV-2 as a novel β genus coronavirus that belongs to the species Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome-related Coronaviruses (SARSr-CoV).
- 2) Development of more specific and accurate diagnostic assays.
- 3) Early geographical and chronological tracking of emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants.
- 4) Has contributed to the adoption and update of public health measurements to contain the COVID-19 pandemic.
- 5) The development and update of vaccines and drugs against COVID-19.
- 6) The prediction of potential SARS-CoV-2 escape variants against which the established vaccines and drugs won't be effective.
- 7) And last but not least, NGS will continue, also in the post-pandemic phase, to be indispensable in monitoring COVID-19 and managing measures against its spread by providing and updating insights into genomes of SARS-CoV-2 and its emerging variants, and their global geographical appearance and distribution, especially if COVID-19 becomes a recurrent 'seasonal' infectious disease. NGS will continue to be essential tool for a global COVID-19 surveillance, alert and response system.